

IMMUNOPATHOGENESIS OF LICHEN PLANUS

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Abstract. The pathogenesis of lichen planus is still not fully understood, but there are several theories that explain its development. One of the main theories suggests the autoimmune nature of the disease, in which the body's immune system attacks its own skin cells and mucous membranes. A possible role in this process belongs to the activation of T-lymphocytes, which provoke inflammatory reactions. The contribution of genetic factors, viral infections and neurological disorders is also discussed. All these theories emphasize the complexity and multifactorial mechanisms of development of lichen planus.

Key words Immunopathogenesis , Inflammatory skin reactions, Molecular immunologists

The immunopathogenesis of LP is associated with a T-cell autoimmune reaction. The inflammatory cells involved in this process consist of T-helper cells, T-cytotoxic lymphocytes, natural killer cells and dendritic cells [91, p. 631–643]. Activation of T cells is a central link in the pathogenesis of LP. Their accumulations at the level of the epidermal-dermal junction lead to apoptosis of basal keratinocytes [106, p. 527–532]. Theoretically, the latter can be induced by CXCR 3 and CCR 5 signaling pathways initiated by both T cells and keratinocytes [60, p. 167–174]. In the early stages of the disease, T cells are predominantly located at the level of the epidermis and epidermal-dermal junction [60, p. 167–174].

In the pathogenesis of the disease, the role of autoreactive clones is assumed T cells, which have a direct effect on keratinocytes , which leads to impaired apoptosis of epidermal cells. In the latter case, keratinocytes and Langerhans cells recognize drug-antigen complexes as foreign [15, p. 5]. The autoimmune theory of the disease is logical, on the one hand, due to the participation of a large pool of T lymphocytes in the skin biopsy, and on the other, due to the frequent combination of LP with other pathologies of the body [103, p. 89–94]. It should be noted that CD 8+ predominate among T cells · T - (cytotoxic) lymphocytes. The latter are closely located with mononuclear cells - histiocytes. The question always remains open for us: why is the infiltrate of lymphocytes and histiocytes located in the lichenoid infiltrate close to the epidermis, supposedly squeezing and pressing it tightly? We believe that the

answer to this question should be sought in long-term antigenic persistence in keratinocyte cells . It is likely that there is a large number of virus antigens of various origins that induce activation of CD 4 + and CD 8 + T -lymphocytes, and also promotes the release of both pro-inflammatory and post-inflammatory cytokines of various levels [62, p. 108–112; 95, p. 531]. Among these pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokines are interleukins (IL)-1, -2, -4, -6, -10 and -31. They promote increased expression of molecules called ICAM -1 (intercellular adhesion molecules) on antigen-presenting cells such as Langerhans cells , histiocytes and dendritic cells. This mechanism indirectly, through the major histocompatibility complex, affects keratinocytes , which leads to an acceleration of apoptosis of the latter [59, p. 597–609]. Overexpression is observed in lesions chemokines associated with CCR 5, as well as target chemokines CXCR 3 [61, 261–268; 108, p. 1003–1009]. This correlation suggests that self-control mechanisms and induction of keratinocytes themselves are involved in T cell migration . In addition, Langerhans cells can be induced CCR 6-mediated chemokines [60, p. 167–174]. Activated T cells stimulate a T helper type 1 (Th 1) response, which leads to the removal of keratinocytes by immune cells [61, p. 261–268]. Type 1 T helper cells are regulated and activated through type 2 toll -like receptors [61, p. 261–268]. NK (natural killer) cells can also be detected in skin biopsies of patients with LP [36, p. 724–730]. They may be involved in the pathogenesis of the disease through cytotoxic activation and are capable of releasing proinflammatory cytokines [36, p. 724–730].

One of the main pathogenetic mechanisms in LP is an increase in apoptosis keratinocytes while reducing T-cell apoptosis [72, p. 219–222]. Activated cytotoxic T cells can regulate Fas ligands and induce apoptosis keratinocytes at the level of the spinous layer of the epidermis [56, p. 487–493]. NK cells and cytotoxic T cells can also induce cell apoptosis through granzyme B / perforin ways. According to some authors, these apoptotic cells are capable of reflecting disease activity [32, p. 179–185]. In the works of A. Ragaz and A. B. Ackerman reported that in the early stages of the disease the number of Langerhans cells increases [94, p. 5–25]. Everyone knows that the latter are powerful antigen- presenting cells and present foreign antigen to T cells . The works of a number of authors indicate that Langerhans cells are most often detected in LP of the oral cavity [88, p. 225–234].

According to a number of authors, in the pathogenesis of patients with LP there is a violation of the mechanisms of immunosuppression through

lymphocyte growth factors [7, p. 348–350; 59, p. 597–609]. All the above pathogenetic mechanisms wear theoretical character .

Conclusions

1. Lichen planus is characterized by a complex immunopathogenesis , which involves various cells of the immune system, including T lymphocytes, and a variety of immune mediators such as cytokines and chemokines .

2. Research shows that autoimmune processes play a significant role in the development of this disease. The discovery of specific antigens associated with lichen planus supports this hypothesis.

3. Dysregulated immune responsiveness and abnormalities in the functioning of the immune system are key factors influencing the pathogenesis of this disease.

The research results highlight the importance of further studying the molecular biological mechanisms of lichen planus to develop new treatment strategies based on the correction of immune disorders.

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